

ORIGIN, DIAGNOSIS AND PREVENTION OF ARRHYTHMIAS

¹Burxonova Nigora

²Aliyev Alisher

³Mahamadiyev Ro'zimurod

^{1,2,3}Samarkand State Medical University, DKTF, Department of Internal Medicine, Cardiology and Functional Diagnostics, 2nd year clinical residents.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14864360>

Introduction

The manifestations of the disease are individual. It all depends on which part of the heart's conduction system or muscle tissue is affected, which area is the source of heart contractions, and how the rhythm changes. Some types of arrhythmia have almost no effect on health and can only cause temporary discomfort, while others cause dangerous complications, the most serious of which is cardiac arrest.

Every year, up to 18 million people worldwide die from cardiovascular disease. Sudden death from its cessation occurs in half of them, mainly in men aged 35-50.

If the disease were detected in time, the largest proportion of these deaths could be prevented. However, this is not simple, because in some cases the disorders do not manifest themselves in any way. People who are overweight, have diabetes, hypertension and high blood cholesterol should be especially vigilant.

In the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems, Tenth Revision (ICD-10), arrhythmia is classified under several codes in Chapter IX, Diseases of the Circulatory System.

Research methods and materials

arrhythmia associated with congenital anomalies and developmental defects;

arrhythmia associated with structural and functional changes in the heart as a result of inflammatory diseases, injuries, valve damage, cardiomyopathy, ischemic heart disease;

arrhythmia that occurs against the background of diseases of other organs or taking medications;

Idiopathic arrhythmia - a change in heart rhythm that occurs for unknown reasons.

Depending on the variation in heart rate, arrhythmia is divided into two types:

bradycardia - slow rhythm, heart rate less than 60 beats per minute;

Fevral, 2025-Yil

Tachycardia - an accelerated rhythm, the frequency of which is more than 100 times per minute.

At the same time, irregular and irregular contractions of the heart muscle (fibrillation) or extra beats (extrasystole) are more common, which can lead to a partial or complete interruption of the heart's contractions (blockade).

Depending on the location of the source of the abnormal rhythm that disrupts the heartbeat, there are supraventricular arrhythmias, which are located in the atria or atrioventricular node, and ventricular arrhythmias, which are located in the ventricles of the heart.

Research results:

Electrolyte and metabolic disorders that often cause arrhythmias include: hypo- or hyperkalemia - low or high levels of potassium in the blood; hypomagnesemia - low magnesium levels; hypocalcemia - low calcium levels; acidosis or alkalosis - serious disturbances in the pH level of the blood.

Doctors and scientists cannot explain the origin of some arrhythmias; such diseases are called idiopathic;

"Idiopathic" is a medical term used by doctors to describe diseases for which the exact cause cannot be explained.

Summary: Holter monitoring is an ECG that records the heart's rhythm throughout the day. For this, electrodes are attached to the person's chest and a portable sensor is worn on the belt, which records heart activity throughout the day. In this case, the patient records the time of physical activity, sleep, food intake or medication in a special diary. This study helps to detect attacks of arrhythmia that are difficult to catch with a regular ECG and to identify their trigger.

Echocardiography, or ultrasound of the heart, allows the doctor to assess the condition of the heart muscle and identify any structural and functional changes in it.

Exercise tests, or stress tests, are used to diagnose rhythm disorders that occur only during physical exertion. To do this, the person is connected to an ECG and asked to run on a treadmill or pedal on an exercise bike to assess how the heart responds to the load.

An electrophysiological study (EPS) can detect serious heart rhythm disturbances. It is an invasive procedure that can only be performed in a hospital setting under general anesthesia. During the classic test, a doctor inserts a thin tube into a vein in the arm, armpit, or neck and threads it through the large blood vessels to the heart. The tube is equipped with a camera to record an electrocardiogram from inside, which allows the exact location of the disturbances to be determined.

REFERENCES

1. Andryev S. et al. Experience with the use of memantine in the treatment of cognitive disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 282-288.
2. Antsiborov S. et al. Association of dopaminergic receptors of peripheral blood lymphocytes with a risk of developing antipsychotic extrapyramidal diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 29-35.
3. Asanova R. et al. Features of the treatment of patients with mental disorders and cardiovascular pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 545-550.
4. Begbudiyev M. et al. Integration of psychiatric care into primary care //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 551-557.
5. Bo'Riyev B. et al. Features of clinical and psychopathological examination of young children //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 558-563.
6. Borisova Y. et al. Concomitant mental disorders and social functioning of adults with high-functioning autism/asperger syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 36-41.
7. Ivanovich U. A. et al. Efficacy and tolerance of pharmacotherapy with antidepressants in non-psychotic depressions in combination with chronic brain ischemia //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 409-414.
8. Nikolaevich R. A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 898-903.
9. Novikov A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 413-419.
10. Pachulia Y. et al. Assessment of the effect of psychopathic disorders on the dynamics of withdrawal syndrome in synthetic cannabinoid addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 240-244.
11. Pachulia Y. et al. Neurobiological indicators of clinical status and prognosis of therapeutic response in patients with paroxysmal schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 385-391.

Fevral, 2025-Yil

12. Pogosov A. et al. Multidisciplinary approach to the rehabilitation of patients with somatized personality development //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 245-251.
13. Pogosov A. et al. Rational choice of pharmacotherapy for senile dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 230-235.
14. Pogosov S. et al. Gnostic disorders and their compensation in neuropsychological syndrome of vascular cognitive disorders in old age //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 258-264.
15. Pogosov S. et al. Prevention of adolescent drug abuse and prevention of yatrogenia during prophylaxis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 392-397.
16. Pogosov S. et al. Psychogenetic properties of drug patients as risk factors for the formation of addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 186-191.
17. Prostyakova N. et al. Changes in the postpsychotic period after acute polymorphic disorder //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 356-360.
18. Prostyakova N. et al. Issues of professional ethics in the treatment and management of patients with late dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 158-165.
19. Prostyakova N. et al. Sadness and loss reactions as a risk of forming a relationship together //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 252-257.
20. Prostyakova N. et al. Strategy for early diagnosis with cardiovascular diseaseisomatized mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 166-172.
21. Rotanov A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 267-272.
22. Rotanov A. et al. Diagnosis of depressive and suicidal spectrum disorders in students of a secondary special education institution //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 309-315.
23. Rotanov A. et al. Elderly epilepsy: neurophysiological aspects of non-psychotic mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 192-197.
24. Rotanov A. et al. Social, socio-cultural and behavioral risk factors for the spread of hiv infection //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 49-55.
25. Rotanov A. et al. Suicide and epidemiology and risk factors in oncological diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 398-403.

Fevral, 2025-Yil

26. Sedenkov V. et al. Clinical and socio-demographic characteristics of elderly patients with suicide attempts //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 273-277.
27. Sedenkov V. et al. Modern methods of diagnosing depressive disorders in neurotic and affective disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 361-366.
28. Sedenkova M. et al. Basic principles of organizing gerontopsychiatric assistance and their advantages //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 63-69.
29. Sedenkova M. et al. Features of primary and secondary cognitive functions characteristic of dementia with delirium //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 56-62.
30. Sedenkova M. et al. The possibility of predicting the time of formation and development of alcohol dependence: the role of genetic risk, family weight and its level //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 173-178.
31. Shamilov V. et al. Disorders of decision-making in the case of depression: clinical evaluation and correlation with eeg indicators //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 198-204.
32. Solovyova Y. et al. Protective-adaptive complexes with codependency //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 70-75.
33. Solovyova Y. et al. Suicide prevention in adolescents with mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 303-308.
34. Solovyova Y. et al. The relevance of psychotic disorders in the acute period of a stroke //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 212-217.
35. Spirkina M. et al. Integrated approach to correcting neurocognitive defects in schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 76-81.

MODERN SCIENCE
& RESEARCH